

The Development of Improved Lamination Methods for Damage Resistant Stiffeners in Large GRP Ships

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ABSTRACT

Specimens representative of GRP ship hull/frame structures have been tested by a slow pull-off technique. The effect of three loading modes on bondline stress distribution and overall test system compliance has been studied. The most severe loading mode has been identified and used to simulate the effect of shock loading on the structures.

It has been found beneficial to selectively increase the compliance of ship hull/frame structures in certain regions, to allow greater work input prior to the first indications of crack damage. This increase in compliance can be achieved by reducing the stiffness of the top-hat web/flange corner, and using a toughened resin in and around the bondline.

INTRODUCTION

Top-hat stiffeners are in widespread use in the GRP shipbuilding industry since they can be readily tailored to the complex curvatures of hulls, and provide built-in buoyancy by the fabrication technique of laminating over rigid polymeric foam cores. A common method involves initial fabrication of an unstiffened hull, and unstiffened flat panels for deck and bulkheads. Rigid form cores are then bonded to these unstiffened structures in the regions where stiffness is desired, and GRP laminations are built up over the cores.

Top-hat stiffeners usually perform satisfactorily, however, under certain loading conditions it is possible to fail the bond between the stiffener and the hull, producing significant stiffness reductions in the structure. A case in point is the effect of underwater shock loading on the hull structure of GRP mine counter measure vessels (MCMVs) (1). To provide a measure of damage tolerance to MCMV hulls, the stiffener flanges are through-bolted to the hull structure below the waterline, using titanium fasteners (2,3). This is only a partial solution to the problem, since any failure initiates at a location remote from the bolt, with the bolt acting as a crack arrestor. To achieve a fundamental improvement in performance, it is necessary to inhibit crack initiation. Further, it is essential that any technique developed should be capable of ready implementation by shipyard fabrication methods, and should also be easily repairable.

PRIOR STUDIES

Previous work (4,5) by the present authors, studying representative woven roving GRP top-hat stiffened specimens by slow pull-off testing, had established several factors relevant to their performance, as follows:

- The loading mode determines both the load at crack initiation and whether failure is progressive or catastrophic.
- Other potentially cheaper mechanical fasteners can function as crack arrestors in a similar manner to titanium through-bolts. However, no mechanical fastener inhibits crack initiation, which is apparently controlled by the properties of the conventional polyester resin laminating matrix.
- Crack initiation occurs at the stiffener/hull bondline under the heel of the stiffener web. The use of a high toughness laminating matrix in this region can inhibit crack initiation and increase dramatically the load and work input required to fail the specimen. This improvement is a result of both the relatively low modulus of the high toughness matrix compared to polyester resin, producing a stress redistribution away from the stress concentration at the crack initiation site, and the much higher failure strain of the high toughness matrix compared to polyester resin.

The results of this previous work were compared with a finite element stress analysis (6) of the effects of different loading configurations on stiffener frame/hull connections in GRP ships. The results were found to be consistent with the predictions of the analysis, and the following conclusions were drawn from the comparison.

- The loading configuration influences markedly the magnitude and direction of bending stresses in the webs of a top-hat stiffener. This in turn influences the nature of the stress concentration in the frame/hull connection under the heel of the stiffener web, affecting the crack initiation load and the failure sequence.
- Following on from this point, stiffness reductions in the stiffener web and flange should reduce the magnitude of frame/hull bondline stress concentrations and improve their performance.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

This experimental programme was designed to clarify several aspects of the prior work. The particular points of interest were as follows:

- The finite element analysis and the prior experimental work has suggested a particular loading mode not previously used, to be the most severe available for slow pull-off testing. This loading mode would be studied to confirm or disprove the prediction.
- A test of the hypotheses that stiffness reductions in the webs and flanges of stiffeners could be beneficial.
- Further study of the use of high toughness laminating matrices in the stiffener/hull bond region.

SPECIMEN FABRICATION

Examination of these aspects required the construction of three specimen variants. The method of stiffened panel lamination and test specimen cutting from panels is described in detail in (4) and typical specimens are illustrated in (4) and (5). The three specimen variants in this work were as follows:

Unreinforced

These specimens are representative, at approximately $2/3$ scale, of a typical below water-line MCMV hull stiffener with a $7\frac{1}{2}^\circ$ inclined top-hat side web. 21 plies of Fothergill and Harvey Y920 woven roving fabric of $81\frac{1}{2}$ gm/m² were used in the base panel, and 12 plies of the same fabric for the stiffener. Six plies of a 630 gm/m² unidirectional glass roving tape were laminated into the stiffener top between the woven roving plies, and glass roving bundles were used as an infill at the stiffener flange/web corner. Lamination was by Cellobond A2785CV polyester resin throughout. The woven roving plies in the stiffener were all of full width from flange edge to edge. The cross section of these specimens is indicated by the dashed line outline in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Thin Web and Flange, and Standard (Dotted Line) Construction Specimens

Thin Web and Flange Specimens

To achieve thinner webs and flanges, woven roving plies were laid up such that they only formed the top, one side web and one flange of the stiffener. The plies were laid alternately from each side of the core. Figure 1 shows the lay-up sequence and the reduction in web and flange thickness compared to the standard unreinforced construction. The top of the frame is identical for both construction methods, maintaining the overall rib stiffening function.

Partial Lamination with a Toughened Resin System

The toughened resin system used was a development resin supplied by Scott Bader Limited, coded CRC1027. It consists of an elastomer modified system dispersed in styrene, and its chemistry can be altered to give various degrees of flexibility. The resin was cured with 1 wt % of Scott Bader Catalyst M (MEKP) and 2 wt % of accelerator E (Co salt).

The lay-up was of the thin web and flange type, as shown in Figure 1. CRC1027 was used for the top seven plies of the base panel, the corner infill roving bundles, the first four woven roving plies on each side of the stiffener, and the associated first unidirectional tape ply on the stiffener top. The bottom 14 plies of the base panel and the other plies in the stiffener used the conventional A2785CV resin.

The toughened resin was used in exactly the same manner as a conventional wet lay-up polyester resin.

SPECIMEN TESTING

The top-hat specimens were all tested in triplicate on a 570kN capacity Mand servo-hydraulic testing machine at a displacement rate of 1mm/min. The base panel of the specimen was clamped to the bed of the test machine using a 50mm square steel bar centrally located. An evenly distributed load was applied over

the area of the stiffener frame top via a 125mm wide shackle.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The detailed results of the slow pull-off tests of the top-hat section specimens are presented in Table 1. Representative load/displacement records for the various specimen types are shown in Figure 2. The failure pattern varied according to the specimen type.

Specimen Type	Max. Load kN	Secant Stiffness kNmm ⁻¹	Total Work Done J	Work to First Load Drop J
Unreinforced	18.2	5.0 (5-14kN)	76.3	24.9
	18.8	5.0	73.5	26.4
	18.2	5.0	47.6	24.2
Thin web and flange	23.2	5.3 (8-18kN)	54.3	54.3
	21.5	5.1	48.2	48.2
	18.2	4.9	41.5	36.2
Thin web and flange, partially laminated with Scott Bader CRC1027	31.8	3.5 (8-24kN)	282.0	144.6
	30.2	3.4	253.7	145.2
	30.5	3.5	232.6	141.6

Table 1 Results of Slow Pull-Off Tests Using Centre Clamping and Distributed Frame Loading

Unreinforced

The load/displacement records were essentially linear up to 15-16kN load, as can be seen in Figure 2, at which point small cracks initiated in the bondline under the heel of the stiffener web, as illustrated by Figure 5a in (4), accompanied by slight load drops. The load increased further until at approximately 18-19kN one flange parted from the base panel by rapid crack propagation along most of the bondline, with the load falling to 8-9kN. The toe of the flange remained attached to the base panel, and further displacement was required to completely separate the flange. Cracking was evident in the bondline of the flange that was still attached to the base panel after the test.

Figure 2 Load/Displacement Records for Standard, Thin Web and Flange Specimens

Thin Web and Flange Specimens

As may be seen from Table 1 and Figure 2, the load/displacement records were linear to failure at maximum loads equal to or greater than those for the baseline unreinforced specimens. No damage was visible in the bondline prior to failure. The stiffener flange separated from the base panel at peak load, leaving part of the lowest flange ply still attached to the base panel and supporting a small load. In all cases, damage was apparent on only one side of the stiffener frame at the end of the test.

Thin Web and Flange Specimens Partially Laminated with CRC1027 Resin

The load/displacement records for these specimens were essentially linear to failure, as may be seen from the representative record in Figure 2, at peak loads substantially higher than observed for the other two specimen variants, as shown in Table 1. Prior to peak load, surface cracking of the base panel occurred next to the central clamp as the base panel flexed. Failure at peak load was by partial separation of one flange from the base panel, accompanied by a rapid load drop. The load then slowly increased until the second flange suddenly but partially separated from the base panel, at which point failure was considered complete.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

That the mode of loading top-hat specimens influences the stress distribution within them and the manner in which they fail was first discussed in Reference 5, and this behaviour has been confirmed in this present work. Reference to Figure 3 shows that the loading mode used in this work is more severe (in terms of lower peak load attained and work done up to first load drop) than the previously used loading modes, as predicted in the study in Reference 5.

The experimental data in Reference 5 were compared with a theoretical finite element stress analysis of the behaviour of top-hat stiffened panels loaded in various modes (Reference 6). This analysis indicated that the bending stresses induced in the web of the stiffener during loading have a dramatic effect on the stress distribution in the stiffener/base panel bondline. This effect is best illustrated by reference to Figure 4. If one considers two conditions, single (central) clamping as used in the tests herein, and two clamp loading, with the base panel clamped on either side of the stiffener only, it will be appreciated that flexure of the base panel due to tensile loading of the stiffener will be in opposite directions for the two loading modes. These flexures induce bending in the stiffener webs, and the direction of these bending stresses are also in opposite directions for the two loading modes, as shown in Figure 4A. The effect that these bending stresses have on the bondline stress distribution is shown in Figure 4B. It is clear that a stress concentration exists under the heel of the stiffener web (where failure usually initiates) in both cases, but it is tensile for single clamp loading and compressive for two clamp loading. For three clamp loading, in which the base panel is restrained both within the

Figure 3 Load/Displacement Records for Unreinforced Specimens Using Various Loading Modes

Figure 4 Stress Distribution in Stiffener Flange Region

stiffener and on either side of it, base panel flexure is constrained, and a bondline stress distribution intermediate between those for single and two clamp loading is produced. This analysis applied in all cases when the imposed load is distributed uniformly across the top of the stiffener. If the load is localised to the centre of the stiffener top, as in the study in Reference 5, the stiffener top can flex and at least partially relax the bending stresses in the stiffener web. It is predicted that this bending stress relaxation will produce a reduced stress concentration of the form shown in Figure 4B. This prediction is borne out by the result in Figure 3 for single clamp loaded specimens where the peak load attained is lower in the case where the load was applied uniformly across the top of the stiffener.

This foregoing analysis explains why the load at which gross crack propagation occurs changes with loading mode, i.e. the high tensile stress concentration for single clamp loading produces a low failure load, and vice versa for three clamp loading. However, the stress analysis does not explain why a slow, progressive crack propagation is observed for three clamp loading, and rapid crack propagation occurs in one and two clamp loading. This difference arises from the effect that the change in loading mode has on the stiffness of the test system.

The three clamp loading mode has produced a system with an overall low compliance, and a consequent rapid load drop for an increment of crack growth. This rapidly falling load becomes insufficient to maintain the high force required for crack propagation, due to the relatively small crack tip stress concentration factor in this case. By contrast, when single clamp loaded, the load drops at a lower rate as a function of crack length, due to the overall higher initial system compliance. This behaviour, coupled with the very high geometric crack tip stress concentration factor when single clamp loaded, results in the relatively low force necessary for crack propagation being maintained. Thus, crack arrest occurs in three clamp loading, and catastrophic failure occurs in single clamp loading, even though the stored energy at crack initiation (i.e. work done to first load drop) is higher in the former case than the latter.

Two points of practical significance for the construction of shock-resistant GRP hulls arise from this analysis. Firstly, crack initiation and arrest is a function of the loading mode and the overall system stiffness. Consequently, the currently used bolts in the structure that are necessarily remote from the crack initiation site should have little effect on crack initiation behaviour, as is observed in practice. However, the bolts do function as crack arrestors, conferring damage tolerance to the structure. Secondly, it is common practice to laminate blocks of wood into the tops of stiffeners to act as machinery attachment points. These machinery seats usually lie across the whole width of the stiffener top. The stress analysis, supported by the experimental observations suggests that the shock performance of the structure may be enhanced by using a narrow machinery seat at the stiffener centre line, this permitting stiffener top flexure and consequent relief of any web bending stresses induced.

The theory advanced in Reference 5 that increased stiffener frame web and flange compliance would improve the pull-off performance was tested by reducing the web and flange thicknesses. Although this thickness reduction did not affect the specimen stiffness (see Table 1) in the test direction, an increase in peak load and an average increase of about 80% in the work input required to initiate damage was observed for the thin flange and web construction compared to the standard construction. If the thin flange and web frame were used, it seems likely that an enhanced shock performance could result combined with a desirable reduction in hull weight. Of course, the stiffening function of the frame should be maintained, and this requires the stiffener web to have sufficient shear and buckling stiffness to maintain the position of the stiffener top relative to the hull, within acceptable limits, when the hull is loaded. Any reduction in stiffener web thickness will increase the section stresses and deformations, and this will constrain the thickness reduction possible. Consequently, the optimum design of stiffener will probably be a compromise involving shock performance, mechanical stiffness requirements, weight and production cost factors.

Property \ Resin		A2785CV Previous Data*	A2785CV This Study	CRC1027	
				Test Speed 2mm/min	Test Speed 0.5mm/min
Tensile Modulus	GPa	3.4-3.6	2.3	0.34-0.4 (Initial)	0.18-0.28 (Initial)
Tensile Strength	MPa	41-46	28	23-27 (Stress at 'Elastic Limit')	14-19 (Stress at 'Elastic Limit')
Strain to Failure	%	1.2-1.8	1.2	63-94	88-125

* The previous data is a combination of results obtained by both the Ministry of Defence (Reference 2) and the authors (Reference 8).

Table 2 Mechanical Properties of Matrix Resins

The idea that local stiffness reductions can enhance shock performance is also inherent in the use of CRC1027 which has a much lower modulus than the conventional A2785CV polyester resin matrix, as shown in Table 2.

The considerable performance improvement produced by the use of CRC1027 resin on both sides of the bondline is obvious from Table 1 and Figure 2. Peak load increases of more than 45% and a tripling of the work input to initiate fracture were observed compared to geometrically similar specimens totally laminated with A2785CV resin. This performance improvement has arisen as a result of the following factors:

- The large bulk of CRC1027 beneath the bondline will strain more than the 10 times higher modulus polyester, hence storing more elastic energy at any particular load value, leading to a higher work input.
- The reduction in web stiffness and web/flange corner stiffness will ease specimen deformation in this region. This produces an effective reduction of the stress concentration in the bondline, and a consequent higher load to initiate failure.

The highly compliant and tough nature of the resin combined with a UTS similar to that of the conventional A2785CV resin has allowed a large bulk of highly strained resin to perform a useful load-bearing function, and consequently store an increased quantity of elastic energy. When the resin failure stress is reached, however, flange separation by crack propagation is rapid, since the large reservoir of elastic energy can be readily released to form crack surfaces due to the overall compliant single clamp test arrangement.

An indirect comparison with tests on titanium-bolted specimens (representative of current MCMV hull fabrication practice) indicates that the work input required to initiate gross damage in the partially CRC1027 laminated specimens is more than twice that for the bolted specimens. It appears likely that a hull construction could be produced with an enhanced shock performance if tough resins of the CRC1027 type were used. This could also produce cost reductions and avoid technical problems associated with the titanium bolts and their insertion procedure. However, the marked strain-rate sensitivity of CRC1027 should be borne in mind, since all the tests in this work were at slow rates. It is likely that the relative performance of the tough matrices and conventional polyester resins will change at shock loading rates. Consequently, it is essential that the production methods suggested incorporating local toughening be assessed at shock loading rates prior to practical adoption.

CONCLUSIONS

- Centre clamping with distributed frame loading is the most severe method of slow pull-off test for top-hat specimens. This test mode produces specimen damage at the lowest loads and for the least work input of all the slow pull-off tests studied. This result confirms the results of a finite element stress analysis of various modes of transverse loading top-hat stiffener frames.
- The overall compliance characteristics of the loading system determine whether crack propagation is progressive or catastrophic.
- An increase in compliance of the stiffener webs and flanges has a beneficial effect. Increases in both load capacity and the work input required to initiate failure are produced by the use of thinner webs and flanges.
- The use of a toughened matrix can increase the peak load capacity and the work input required to initiate failure. For the best results, the toughened matrix should be used for lamination both above and below the bondline. The use of an elastomer modified resin that can be laminated in the conventional manner has shown considerable promise.
- The results obtained in this work, particularly those for construction incorporating toughened matrices, require confirmation at shock loading rates before the lamination methods can be recommended for adoption for MCMV hull construction.

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